

Diastereoselective opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols : Application in the studies directed toward the synthesis of octenoic acid moiety of cryptophycins[†]

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Manuscript received 6 September 1999

Stereoselective synthesis of the 5,7-acetonide of (2*E*,5*S*,6*R*,7*R*,8*S*)-5,7,8-trihydroxy-6-methyl-8-phenyl-2-octenoic acid ethyl ester (**3**), an isomer of **2**, precursor of the epoxy octenoic acid moiety **1** present in depsipeptide cryptophycins is achieved where diastereoselective opening of an intermediate trisubstituted epoxy alcohol **4** based on a radical-mediated method developed by us earlier furnishes the crucial '2-methyl-1,3-diol' moiety of the C₅-C₇ segment of the molecule. The protocol also allows the synthesis of some of the other 16 diastereomers of this hydroxy acid having 4 chiral centres which can find useful applications in the structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies of these potent antitumor agents.

The depsipeptide cryptophycins (Scheme 1) found in the terrestrial blue-green algae (cyanobacterium) *Nostoc* sp. GSV 224 and ATCC 53789 are potent antitumor and antifungal peptolides¹. Over 20 structurally related cryptophycins are present in the GSV 224 strain in various proportions. The major component in each alga, cryptophycin A, shows excellent activity against a broad spectrum of solid tumors, including drug-resistant ones, implanted in mice^{1,2}. The potent cytotoxic activities and the structural complexities associated with these molecules have attracted the attention of synthetic organic chemists worldwide. Several total syntheses of some of these molecules, mostly cryptophycins C and D, have already been reported³. For the synthesis of cryptophycins A and B, the olefinic precursors C and D have been epoxidized with mCPBA leading to a mixture of diastereomers at the epoxide site^{3d,e}. Only in one report^{3f}, a stereoselective synthesis of cryptophycins A and B has been reported starting from α -

O-silylated aldehyde derived from chiral mandelic acid. A number of synthetic analogs of cryptophycins have also been synthesized and biologically evaluated⁴. But, all the analogs have so far been designed by altering amino acid residues leaving the octenoic acid component untouched. We envisaged that a simple synthetic protocol to construct some of the structural variants of the crucial epoxy octenoic acid segment **1** will give an access to synthetic analogs of cryptophycins useful for structure-activity relationship studies, preclinical evaluation, and human clinical trials. Herein we report the preliminary results of our study on the stereoselective synthesis of the 5,7-acetonide of (2*E*,5*S*,6*R*,7*R*,8*S*)-5,7,8-trihydroxy-6-methyl-8-phenyl-2-octenoic acid-ethyl ester (**3**), precursor of one of the diastereomers of the epoxy octenoic acid moiety **1**. The key feature in our synthesis is the application of an excellent method developed by us recently⁵ for the synthesis of chiral 2-methyl-1,3-diol by radical-mediated anti-Markovnikov opening of

Scheme 1. Retrosynthetic analysis of cryptophycins

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary

trisubstituted epoxy alcohol **3** at the more substituted carbon using cp_2TiCl in the presence of cyclohexa-1,4-diene which acts as a donor of hydrogen atoms. This furnished the crucial '2-methyl-1,3-diol' moiety of the $\text{C}_5\text{-C}_7$ segment of the molecule, thus highlighting the practical applicability of our method in multistep synthesis of natural products.

Results and Discussion

The stereotriads **5-8** (Scheme 2), the four possible diastereomers of the 2-methyl-1,3-diol framework, appear ubiquitously in various propionate-derived polyketide natural

Scheme 2. Radical-mediated opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohols.

products. Recently, we have developed a method for the stereoselective synthesis of the stereotriads **5-7** which involves opening of the trisubstituted epoxy alcohols **9-12**, prepared easily from the corresponding 2-methylbut-2-en-1-ols⁵.

According to our study as shown in Scheme 2, both *syn* and *anti* epoxy alcohols **9** and **10**, respectively, on epoxide ring opening with cp_2TiCl -cyclohexa-1,4-diene give *syn,syn*-diol **5** as the major product, whereas the products from the epoxy alcohols **11** and **12** depend on the relative sizes of R_1 and R_2 . When R_1 is bigger than R_2 , the major product is *anti,syn* diol **6**. With smaller R_1 , the *syn,anti* product **7** predominates. Unlike the classical $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ -type hydride opening of epoxides where exclusive diastereoselectivity is observed, our radical-mediated reaction was feared to lead to the epimerization of the radical bearing centre. However, excellent diastereoselectivity was observed during the hydrogen abstraction process in all the cases studied by us. This was attributed to the possibility of the reaction going via a six-membered cyclic Ti^{IV} -intermediate, where the stereochemistries at C_1 and C_3 and the sizes of R_1 and R_2 were the deciding factors for the observed facial selectivity.

For 1,3-*syn* substrates, originating from the epoxides **9**

and **10**, the cyclic six-membered intermediate **I** (Fig. 1) takes a chair-type conformation where the approach of the hydrogen atom is antiperiplanar to the $\alpha\text{-C-O}$ bond which, having the lowest σ^* orbital energy, occupies, in the reactive conformer, a position eclipsing the singly occupied p -orbital at the radical centre enabling maximum overlap lowering the energy of the p -orbital and, consequently, minimizing the free energy of activation for the reaction. The 1,3-*anti*-diols resulting from the epoxides **11** and **12**, on the other hand, comes from a twist-boat conformation **II** (Fig. 1)⁶ where the sizes of R_1 and R_2 decide the stereochemical

outcome of the reaction. In fact, it is the product stability here which probably decides the course of the reaction giving a thermodynamically controlled product. The C_2 -methyl possibly takes a position where it is closer to the smaller one of R_1 and R_2 with two dihedral angles of about 90 and 30 degrees.

Fig. 1. Transition state models for epoxide opening reaction : chair conformation (I) for *syn,syn* product **5**; twist-boat conformation (II) for *anti,syn* (or *syn,anti*) product **6** (or **7**).

In cryptophycins the C_5 - and C_7 -hydroxyls are *anti* necessitating to start our synthesis with an epoxide like **11** or **12** which should give 5,6-*syn*-6,7-*anti*-product like **6** (with $\text{R}_1 > \text{R}_2$), or 5,6-*anti*-6,7-*syn*-diol as **7** (with $\text{R}_1 < \text{R}_2$). To explore various possibilities we first started with the ep-

oxide **4** which was prepared from the aldehyde **13**⁷ as outlined in Scheme 3. Addition of Li-enolate of ethyl acetate to the aldehyde **13** gave the allylic alcohol **14** which on LAH reduction followed by selective primary hydroxyl protection as *tert*-butyldiphenylsilyl ether furnished the requisite allylic alcohol **16** in 55% overall yield in three steps. Sharpless kinetic resolution⁸ of **16** with natural (+)-diisopropyl L-tartrate gave the chiral epoxy alcohol **4** in 39%

To carry out the crucial epoxide ring opening reaction, the epoxy alcohol **4** was subjected to Cp_2TiCl -cyclohexa-1,4-diene, according to the procedure reported by us earlier⁵. The diastereomer **18** was formed as the major product in 5 : 1 ratio as determined by ¹H NMR spectrum of the mixture in 80% yield. The minor 6*S*-isomer could be easily separated by silica gel column chromatography after the acetonide protection step. The mixture of diols was next

Scheme 3. Stereoselective synthesis of **3**.

yield (81% yield based on recovered unreacted *R*-allylic alcohol **17**). While the enantiomeric excess of the product **4** is yet to be determined, its diastereomeric assignment was done on the basis of earlier studies and subsequently verified after 2 steps : opening up of the epoxy ring and making acetonide from the resulting diol. The ¹³C NMR signals of the acetonide were used to confirm the 5,7-*anti* relationship of **4**⁹.

converted to acetonides in 90% yield. The major isomer **19** was separated from the mixture by standard silica gel column chromatography. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of **19** showed acetonide methyl signals at δ 25 and 23.93 and that of ketal carbon at 100.65, proving 5,7-*anti* relationship⁹. The energy minimized structure of **19** (Fig. 2) generated by using PCMODEL showed the CH₃-C₆-C₇-CH₂OBn dihedral angle as -95.2° and the CH₃-C₆-C₅-CH₂ as 38.3° in a twist-

boat conformation. It is assumed that similar situation arises in the Ti^{IV} -containing 6-membered reactive conformer (II in Fig. 1) during the epoxide ring opening step confirming our findings that bigger R_1 gives 6-type (*anti,syn*) product.

Fig. 2. Energy minimized conformation of 19 (hydrogens are not shown).

Debenzylation of 19 was followed by oxidation using SO_3 -pyridine complex giving the aldehyde 21. Diastereoselective Grignard addition of $PhMgBr$ to the aldehyde 21 gave the *anti*-product 22 as the major one in 4 : 1 ratio in 68% overall yield from 19. The stereochemical assignment of the newly generated centre was done on the basis of 1H NMR studies. The signals for all the protons at this stage were very well separated making it possible to carry out decoupling studies to make the assignments and determine the coupling constants. The C_8 -H signal appeared as a doublet at δ 4.5 (J 7.6 Hz) and the C_7 -H showed a triplet at 3.35 (J 7.6 Hz). The $J_{5,6}$ was found to be 4.5 Hz. This supported the assigned stereochemistry of 22 having 5,6-*syn*-6,7-*anti*-7,8-*anti* orientations. The energy-minimized structure of 22 (Fig. 3) obtained by using PCMODEL showed a twist-boat conformation with nearly equal $J_{7,8}$ and $J_{6,7}$ values and a smaller $J_{5,6}$ ¹⁰. The theoretical values were in agreement with the experimental coupling constants.

Fig. 3. Energy minimized conformation of 22.

The formation of the *anti*-product as the major diastereomer in the Grignard reaction can be explained by nonchelate controlled Felkin-Anh transition state model¹¹ (Fig. 4) where

Fig. 4. Transition state model for the Grignard addition on the aldehyde 21.

the oxygen-bearing bond at the α -carbon atom lies perpendicular to the aldehyde carbonyl in the reactive conformer. Grignard attack takes place antiperiplanar to this α -C-O bond from the less hindered side (conformer A) giving selectively the *anti*-product.

Protection of the C_8 -hydroxy as PMB-ether was followed by deprotection of primary *O*-silyl ether. The resulting alcohol 24 was oxidized and olefination with stabilized ylide $Ph_3P=CHCO_2Et$ gave the (*E*)- α,β -unsaturated ester 26 in 53% overall yield in 4 steps from 22. Deprotection of PMB-ether gave the benzylic alcohol 3 in 92% yield.

Attempted epoxidation at the C_7 - C_8 segment by mesylation of the benzylic hydroxyl of 3 has given an unexpected product, which is probably a substituted tetrahydrofuran, as the only isolated product. Its formation can be explained by an *in situ* acetonide deprotection followed by a facile intramolecular S_N2 type cyclization involving nucleophilic attack by C_5 -OH on the C_8 -OMs. Structural assignments of this product is currently under study. Efforts are on to make the epoxide from 3 by other methods. Also, reduction of the steric bulk at the C_8 -centre can be attempted to get the 6*S*-isomer as present in naturally occurring cryptophycins as the major product in the epoxide opening step.

Epoxidation of (*R*)-allylic alcohol 17 (Scheme 4), obtained in the Sharpless kinetic resolution step, by mCPBA gave the *syn*-epoxy alcohol 27 as the only isolated diastereomer which was subjected to the epoxide opening reaction giving exclusively the *syn,syn*-product 28. Protection of the diol as acetonide 29 was carried out next to confirm the assigned structure. The ^{13}C NMR of 29 showed acetonide methyls at δ 29.92 and 19.66 and the ketal carbon at 99. This will be utilized to make the 5,6-*syn*-6,7-*syn*-7,8-*anti* isomer of 1.

In conclusion, the radical-mediated opening of trisubstituted epoxy alcohol can be utilized effectively to prepare

Scheme 4. Stereoselective synthesis of *syn,syn* '2-methyl-1,3-diol' 28.

various diastereomers of epoxy octenoic acid component 1 of cryptophycins which will find useful applications in the development of analogous substrates with improved properties. Further studies are currently in progress.

Experimental

NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Gemini 200 or Unity 400 instrument with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard (*J* values expressed in Hz), IR spectra on Shimadzu IR-470 and Perkin-Elmer 283 B spectrophotometers, and mass spectra on VG MICROMASS 70-70H and VG Auti Spec M spectrometers under electron impact (EI), chemical ionization (CI) or liquid secondary ion mass spectrometric (LSIMS) techniques.

All reactions were monitored by TLC carried out on 0.25 mm E. Merck silica gel plates (60F-254) with UV light, I₂, 7% ethanolic phosphomolybdic acid-heat and 2.5% ethanolic anisaldehyde (with 1% AcOH and 3.3% conc. H₂SO₄)-heat as developing agents. Silica gel (finer than 200 mesh, Acme, India) was used for flash column chromatography. All reactions were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere with dry, freshly distilled solvents under anhydrous condition unless otherwise noted. Yields refer to chromatographically and spectroscopically homogeneous materials unless otherwise stated.

The numberings of epoxy octenoic acid 1 are used in all substrates to assign nmr peaks.

Sharpless kinetic resolution of 16. Synthesis of the epoxy alcohol 4 : Activated, powdered 4 Å molecular sieve (200 mg, 20 wt.%) in CH₂Cl₂ (5 ml) were taken in a flame-dried 25-ml round bottom flask under nitrogen atmosphere. After cooling to -20°, a solution of (+)-DIPT (0.052 ml, 0.25 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1 ml) and a solution of Ti(ⁱPrO)₄ (0.06 ml, 0.21 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1 ml), each separately stirred with 4 Å molecular sieve (50 mg) for 15 min, were cannulated sequentially into the reaction flask with stirring. After 20 min, TBHP (3 M in toluene, 0.7 ml) was added to the reaction mixture. It was stirred at the same temperature for 0.5 h. A solution of 16 (1 g, 2.06 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (2

ml), stirred with 4 Å molecular sieve (50 mg) for 15 min prior to the addition, was then cannulated into the reaction mixture and stirring continued for 1 h. An aqueous solution of tartaric acid (30%; 2 ml) was added to it and the temperature was allowed to come to 0°. After 0.5 h, an aq. NaOH solution (30%; 2 ml), saturated with NaCl, was added and stirred at 0° for 0.5 h. It was then taken in a separatory funnel and the organic layer was separated. The aq. layer was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (2×20 ml). The combined organic layer and extracts was washed with brine (20 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification by column chromatography (silica gel, 5–10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant) gave unreacted *R*-allylic alcohol 17 (0.52 g, 52%) and pure epoxide 4 (0.41 g, 39%) : 4 *R*_f = 0.5 (silica gel, 20% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); [α]_D²² -51.6 (*c* 1.7, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz, numberings of 1) δ 7.7–7.2 (15H, m, ArH), 4.56 (2H, ABq, OCH₂Ph), 3.95–3.65 (4H, m, C₃-H, C₅-H, C₈-H₂), 3.52 (1H, ddd, *J* 11.3, 7.2, C₃-H'), 3.2 (1H, t, *J* 5.7, C₇-H), 2.75 (1H, br s, OH), 1.9–1.5 (2H, m, C₄-H₂), 1.25 (3H, s, C₆-CH₃), 1.02 (9H, s, *tert*-butyl).

Epoxide opening of 4. Synthesis of 18 : Freshly fused anhydrous ZnCl₂ (0.54 g, 3.98 mmol) was added at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere to a mixture of cp₂TiCl₂ (0.991 g, 3.98 mmol) and dry activated Zn powder (0.52 g, 7.96 mmol) in dry THF (8 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h while its colour gradually changed from red to dark green. It was then cooled to -20° and a solution of 4 (0.4 g, 0.796 mmol) and 1,4-cyclohexadiene (0.75 ml, 7.96 mmol) in dry THF (2 ml) was added slowly. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature over a period of 2 h and the stirring continued for an additional 4 h while its colour changed from dark green to dark blue. The reaction was then quenched by slow addition of 1 N HCl (20 ml) and the mixture extracted with EtOAc (2×20 ml). The combined EtOAc extracts was washed with 1 N HCl (2×20 ml), water (20 ml) and brine (20 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification by column chromatography (silica gel,

10–20% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant) gave the diol **18** (0.322 g, 80%) as a mixture of 6*R* : 6*S* isomers (5 : 1 ratio) which were separated after the acetonide protection step.

The acetonide 19 : The diol from the previous step (0.31 g, 0.61 mmol) and CSA (14 mg, 0.06 mmol) were dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (4 ml) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (0.15 ml, 1.22 mmol) was added at 0° and the mixture was slowly allowed to come to room temperature in 1 h. It was then quenched by adding saturated aq. NaHCO₃ (5 ml) and extracted with EtOAc (2×5 ml). The combined extracts was washed with brine (5 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), and concentrated. Column chromatography (silica gel, 5–10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant) gave the pure acetonide **19** (0.255 g, 77%) as a major product : **19**, *R*_f = 0.6 (silica gel, 10% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); [α]_D²⁵ 1.84 (*c* 1.36, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz, numberings of **1**) δ 7.7–7.2 (15H, m, ArH), 4.58 (2H, ABq, OCH₂Ph), 4.1 (1H, m, C₅-H), 3.8–3.4 (5H, m, C₃-H₂, C₇-H, C₈-H₂), 1.8–1.5 (2H, m, C₄-H₂), 1.34 and 1.32 (6H, two s, acetonide methyls), 1.04 (9H, s, *tert*-butyl), 0.8 (3H, d, *J* 6.7, C₆-CH₃); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 50 MHz) δ 138.43, 135.52, 133.93, 129.52, 128.3, 127.58, 100.65, 74.72, 73.27, 72, 65.33, 60.45, 36.17, 33.73, 26.86, 25, 23.93, 19.17, 12.05.

Synthesis of Grignard addition product 22, starting from the alcohol 20 : The alcohol **20** (0.22 g, 0.48 mmol) and Et₃N (0.4 ml, 2.9 mmol) were taken in a mixture of dry CH₂Cl₂ and dry DMSO (2.5 ml, 2 : 3) and cooled to 0°. To it was added SO₃-pyridine (0.46 g, 2.9 mmol) portionwise and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at 0°. It was then diluted with ether (10 ml), the organic layer washed with water (3×5 ml), brine (5 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), concentrated *in vacuo*, and used directly in the next reaction. It was dissolved in dry ether (3 ml), cooled to 0° and treated with PhMgBr (0.5 *M* in ether, 1.5 ml). After 10 min, it was quenched by adding saturated NH₄Cl (5 ml), extracted with EtOAc (2×10 ml), washed with brine (10 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), and concentrated *in vacuo*. Column chromatography (silica gel, 5–10% EtOAc in petroleum ether) gave **22** (0.164 g, 64%) as the major product : **22**, *R*_f = 0.5 (silica gel, 15% EtOAc in petroleum ether eluant); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 200 MHz, numberings of **1**) δ 7.7–7.2 (15H, m, ArH), 4.5 (1H, d, *J* 7.6, C₈-H), 4.14 (1H, ddd, *J* 4.5, 4.5 and 8.5, C₅-H), 3.74–3.62 (2H, m, C₃-H₂), 3.35 (1H, t, *J* 7.6, C₇-H), 2.96 (1H, br s, OH), 1.75 (1H, m, C₆-H), 1.6–1.4 (2H, m, C₄-H₂), 1.34 and 1.32 (6H, two s, acetonide methyls), 1.05 (9H, s, *tert*-butyl), 0.85 (3H, d, *J* 6.7, C₆-CH₃).

¹H NMR of **3** (CDCl₃, 200 MHz) : δ 7.45–7.35 (5H, m, ArH), 6.9 (1H, dt, *J* 7 and 16, C₃-H), 5.88 (1H, d, *J* 16, C₂-H), 4.5 (1H, d, *J* 7.6, C₈-H), 4.18 (2H, q, *J* 7, CO₂CH₂CH₃), 3.96 (1H, dt, *J* 4.5 and 8.5, C₅-H), 3.42 (1H, t, *J* 7.5, C₇-

H), 3.02 (1H, br, OH), 2.4–2 (2H, m, C₄-H₂), 1.85 (1H, m, C₆-H), 1.38 and 1.35 (6H, two s, acetonide methyls), 1.26 (3H, t, *J* 7, CO₂CH₂CH₃), 0.42 (3H, d, *J* 6.5, C₆-CH₃).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank U.G.C., New Delhi, for research fellowship to one of them (S.D.) and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for Young Scientist Award Research Grant to the other (T.K.C.).

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